

Additive Manufacturing of Ni/NiCr Thermocouples on Ceramic Substrates by Directed Energy Deposition

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Abstract

The direct integration of temperature sensors into thermally loaded components reduces the number of production steps and enables localized temperature measurements regardless of the selected contour. Directed Energy Deposition (DED) offers high potential for such applications due to its capability for multi-material processing; however, the direct deposition of metallic thermocouple tracks onto electrically insulating ceramic substrates remains challenging. In this study, Ni/NiCr thermocouples were fabricated directly onto thermally sprayed yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) substrates using DED. Process parameters established for depositing Ni/NiCr on metallic steel substrates were found to be unsuitable for ceramic deposition due to excessive energy input and insufficient track formation. Dedicated parameter studies were therefore conducted for Ni and NiCr, focusing on scan velocity, powder mass flow rate, laser beam diameter, focal position, and NiCr powder particle size. The results demonstrate pronounced material- and particle-size-dependent differences in thermal interaction with the ceramic substrate. Fine NiCr powders caused significant heat-affected zones (HAZ) and substrate degradation, whereas coarser powder fractions substantially reduced thermal damage but required adapted focal conditions to achieve electrically functional tracks. Using optimized parameters, a functional Ni/NiCr thermocouple was fabricated and tested up to 300 °C, showing a stable and linear thermoelectric response with a systematic voltage offset relative to a conventional Type K thermocouple.

Keywords:

Directed Energy Deposition, Thermocouples, Multi-Material Application, IN718, Nickel, Yttria-Stabilized Zirconia

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) enables the fabrication of structurally and functionally optimized components that are challenging or unfeasible to realize with conventional manufacturing methods. It allows including complex internal features and locally tailored geometries. [1, 2]. Beyond geometric freedom, a key opportunity is the integration of functional elements such as sensors directly into the manufacturing process. In-process sensor integration can reduce post-processing steps and enables a precise application of sensing structures at locations that are otherwise difficult to access. Importantly, embedding the sensors during fabrication can avoid additional machining features that may affect functionality and compromise structural integrity. One example would be the disturbance of heat flux paths by drilling holes for local temperature measurement in thermally loaded components [3].

Several approaches have been explored to integrate temperature sensing structures onto or into components. Direct-write approaches based on thermal spraying have been used to deposit sensor tracks [4], whereas in drilling applications, thin-film thermocouples have been produced by physical vapor deposition (PVD), enabling sensor thicknesses as thin as 20 μm [5, 6]. However, many of these approaches are inherently multi-step surface processes that require masking and are primarily limited to near-surface application. As a result, the robust integration of sensing structures at defined positions within bulk components and the manufacturing of mechanically stable, application-oriented sensor architectures remain challenging.

Directed Energy Deposition (DED) offers a promising candidate to overcome these limitations. In DED powder or wire feedstock is inserted into a focused heat source, enabling material to be deposited only where needed. The process is well suited for multi-material deposition and, depending on the system, can enable compositional grading through controlled material transitions [7]. This capability provides a pathway to fabricate structural materials as well as functional sensor tracks within a single manufacturing workflow and to place sensor elements at application-relevant locations.

For thermocouple integration, a fundamental requirement is reliable electrical insulation between the thermoelectric materials and the surrounding material. Using ceramic substrates as electrical insulators is attractive, yet the deposition of metallic tracks onto ceramic layers via DED is challenging due to the ceramics' low tolerance to thermal shock and their distinct thermo-physical properties compared to metals [8].

Zhang et al. [9] demonstrated embedded thermocouple concepts in ceramic systems by depositing metallic thermocouple tracks consisting of alumel and chromel onto a ceramic layer of thermally sprayed yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ) and subsequently covering them with an additional ceramic top layer. The sensor was tested up to 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Although a slight offset was observed, the temperature response of the embedded thermocouple corresponded closely with that of a conventional sensor. While such studies underline the potential of embedded thermocouples, the deposition of metallic tracks onto ceramic substrates remains a critical processing challenge, particularly with respect to adhesion, control of the heat-affected zones (HAZ), and repeatable electrical performance.

Although the integration of thermocouples into additively manufactured components has been demonstrated, the approaches rely on multi-step surface processes or embedding strategies that are limited in their geometric freedom and robustness. While DED offers the potential for multi-material integration, systematic studies on the direct deposition of metallic thermocouple tracks onto ceramic substrates remain scarce. In particular, the identification of robust DED process parameters for the deposition of metals onto ceramic substrates, the control of thermal interaction at the metal-ceramic interface, and the resulting electrical functionality of the deposited sensor structures have not been exploited sufficiently.

Therefore, the present study investigates the DED-manufacturing of a thermocouple based on nickel (Ni) and Inconel 718 (IN718) deposited onto an electrically insulating YSZ substrate. The Ni/IN718 material pair is selected as a practical alternative to conventional Ni/NiCr (thermocouple type K)

combinations, leveraging the high relevance and broad availability of IN718 in metallic additive manufacturing. Note that IN718 with its nominal composition of NiCr19NbMo can be considered a suitable substitute for conventional NiCr-Thermocouple compositions. The study aims to (i) evaluate whether process parameters established for metallic substrates can be transferred to a ceramic substrate, (ii) identify dedicated parameter sets for depositing conductive and adherent IN718 and examine the influence of IN718 powder particle size on deposition behavior and ceramic interaction (iii) identify dedicated parameter sets for depositing conductive and adherent Ni tracks. Finally, a functional Ni/IN718 thermocouple is fabricated and its thermoelectric response is assessed in furnace tests up to 300 °C and compared to a conventional thermocouple.

2. Material and Methods

A commercially available Ni powder with a purity of 99.5 wt.% and a particle size distribution between 60 and 150 μm (cf. Table 1) was used for the deposition of the Ni thermocouple track. For IN718, two different powder particle size distributions were investigated in order to assess the influence of the particle size on the deposition behavior and the thermal interaction with the ceramic substrate. The fine powder fraction ranged from 20 to 63 μm , while the coarse fraction ranged from 53 to 150 μm (cf. Table 1). All powders were obtained from VDM Metals GmbH (Werdhol, Germany). The nominal chemical composition of the IN718 powder, according to the supplier specifications, was independent of particle size and consisted of 53.48 – 53.68 wt.% Ni, 18.37 wt.% Cr, approximately 5.11 wt.% Nb, 3 wt.% Mo and balance Fe. The nominal compositions of all powders used in the present study are summarized in Table 1. Powder morphology was analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Representative SEM images of the Ni powder and the two IN718 powder fractions are displayed in Figure 1. All powders exhibited a predominantly spherical particle morphology with isolated but large surface agglomerations.

Figure 1: SEM images of the powder materials used in this study: (a) Ni powder (60-150 μm), (b) IN718 powder with a particle size distribution of 20-63 μm , and (c) IN718 powder with a particle size distribution of 60 - 150 μm .

Table 1: Nominal chemical composition of the nickel and IN718 powder materials used in this study, according to supplier specifications (wt.%).

Material	IN718	IN718	Ni
Particle distribution	20 - 63 μm	60 - 150 μm	60 - 150 μm
Carbon	0.021	0.026	0.002
Manganese	0.03	0.03	0.31
Silicon	0.05	0.06	0.09
Phosphorus	0.003	0.005	-
Sulfur	0.001	0.001	0.0005
Chromium	18.38	18.37	-
Nickel	53.48	53.68	99.5
Molybdenum	2.98	3.03	-
Niobium	5.13	5.11	-
Titanium	0.96	0.95	-
Aluminum	0.54	0.5	-
Cobalt	0.05	0.06	-
Tantalum	0.01	-	-
Boron	0.004	0.004	-
Copper	0.02	0.03	-
Iron	Balance	Balance	Balance

Thermally sprayed YSZ coatings were used as electrically insulating ceramic substrates. The YSZ layers were deposited onto a steel plate made of 100Cr6 (1.3505) bearing steel by the Institute of Energy Materials and Devices at Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany. The ceramic coating thickness was approximately 200 μm and exhibited a lamellar and porous microstructure typical for thermally sprayed ceramic layers. A cross sectional view of the YSZ coating on the steel substrate is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Cross-sectional view of the thermally sprayed YSZ coating on the 100Cr6 steel substrate.

All deposition experiments were carried out using a DED system of type pE3D (ponticon GmbH, Wiesbaden, Germany). The system is equipped with a high-power diode laser (Laserline GmbH, Mühlheim-Kärlich, Germany) with a maximum output of power of 8 kW and a wavelength range between 900 and 1,080 nm. Powder material was delivered coaxially into the laser-induced melt pool using an eight-jet nozzle with working distance of 20 mm. Argon was used as both shielding and carrier gas for all experiments. The shielding gas flow rate and the carrier gas flow rate were kept constant at 14 l/min. All depositions were performed in an open atmosphere under argon shielding.

The experimental program was designed to investigate the deposition of metallic thermocouple materials onto ceramic substrates and to identify suitable process parameters for thermocouple fabrication. Initially, process parameters previously established for the deposition of IN718 on metallic substrates were transferred to the ceramic substrate in order to assess their applicability. Based on the observed limitations, dedicated parameter studies were subsequently conducted for nickel and IN718 deposition on YSZ. For the parameter studies, powder feed rate, laser scan velocity, and laser focus diameter were systematically varied within defined ranges, while laser powder, and shielding and carrier gas conditions were kept constant. The selected ranges of powder mass flow rate differed for Ni and IN718 powders due to differences in powder characteristics and deposition behaviour. In preliminary experiments, the powder mass flow rate was adjusted to ensure a stable powder stream and sufficient material supply to the melt pool without excessive powder accumulation. Based on these observations, the powder mass flow rate was varied within the range of 30–50 g/min for IN718 and kept constant at 33 g/min for Ni in order to isolate the influence of scan velocity on track formation. The influence of powder particle size on the deposition behavior of IN718 was investigated by repeating identical parameter sets for both particle size distributions. All deposited tracks were single-pass tracks.

Metallographic cross-sections of the deposited tracks were prepared by embedding the samples in WEM-REM (Cloeren Technology GmbH, Wegberg, Germany). Subsequently, the samples were progressively ground down to 6 μm using abrasive paper and then polished to 0.25 μm using OP-S (Struers ApS, Ballerup, Denmark) as the polishing medium. The microstructure of the deposited tracks and the substrate-track interface was examined by optical microscopy (OM) and SEM. For OM investigations, specimens were analyzed using the digital microscope VHX-6000 of Keyence (Osaka, Japan). SEM investigations were conducted using a Zeiss EVO 60 XVP with a LaB₆ cathode (Carl Zeiss AG; Oberkochen; Germany) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) detector. During analysis the SEM was operated at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV. The measurements were performed at different magnifications (90 \times - 150 \times). EDS was employed to analyze the elemental distribution across the metal-ceramic interface and to evaluate potential diffusion phenomena. EDS line scans and point analyses were performed at representative locations across the interface.

The electrical conductivity of deposited tracks adhering to the ceramic substrate was evaluated qualitatively by measuring electrical continuity along the track length using external electrical contacts. For thermoelectric characterization, Ni/IN718 thermocouples were fabricated by depositing perpendicular nickel and IN718 tracks intersecting at a single junction. The thermocouples were electrically connected to compensation wires using soldered joints. A conventional Type K thermocouple was placed adjacent to the additively manufactured thermocouple as a reference. Thermoelectric measurements were conducted in a furnace. The temperature was increased at a constant heating rate of 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{h}$. The thermoelectric voltage generated by the printed thermocouple was recorded as a function of the temperature measured by the reference thermocouple.

3. Results and Discussion

Transferability of Metal-Derived Process Parameters to Ceramic Substrate

Process parameters previously established in preliminary parameter studies (not discussed for sake of brevity) for the deposition of IN718 on metallic substrates were initially transferred to the ceramic substrate in order to evaluate their applicability. For deposition on the 100Cr6 steel substrate, a stable parameter window has been identified with laser powers between 2.5 and 4.0 kW, scan velocities ranging from 50 to 150 m/min, and powder mass flow rates between 30 and 60 g/min. These parameters resulted in dilution values between 45 and 60 % and width-to-height ratios between 12 and 17. The dilution was defined as $d = D/(D+H)$, where D represents the cladding depth and H the cladding height [10]. The laser beam diameter was kept constant at 1.2 mm. To assess parameter transferability, identical process parameters were applied to the thermally sprayed YSZ substrate. Figure 3 compares the

deposition behavior of IN718 tracks produced on the steel substrate and on the ceramic substrate under identical processing conditions (laser power 4 kW, powder feed rate 30 g/min, scan velocity 100 m/min, laser beam diameter 1.2 mm).

On the steel substrate, (cf. Figure 3 a) a continuous weld bead with a pronounced mixing zone was formed. A dilution of 56 % and a width-to-height ratio of 16.64 were obtained. In contrast, the application of the same parameters to the ceramic substrate did not result in the formation of continuous tracks. Instead, only isolated powder adhesions were observed on the ceramic surface (Figure 3b,c). In the top-view images, localized surface modification of the ceramic layer was detected, while cross-sectional views revealed the absence of a coherent metallic track. The observed behavior indicates that the high energy input required for deposition on metallic substrates is not compatible with the thermal response of the ceramic coating. The insufficient powder deposition on the ceramic substrate suggests that a reduction in scan velocity and an increase in powder mass flow rate would be required to promote track formation. However, reducing the scan velocity at constant laser power would further increase the local energy input, thereby exacerbating thermal damage to the ceramic substrate. Consequently, a direct transfer of process parameters optimized for metallic substrates to ceramic substrates is not feasible.

Figure 3: a) Comparison of IN718 tracks deposited on (a) a 100Cr6 steel substrate and on a thermally sprayed YSZ substrate shown as (b) top view and (c) cross-sectional view, using identical process parameters.

Based on these observations, a dedicated parameter study was conducted to identify suitable processing conditions for deposition on YSZ. In this study, the laser power was reduced to a minimum of 800 W, and the scan velocity was varied between 2 and 10 m/min in order to limit the thermal load on the ceramic substrate while enabling sufficient powder deposition. The results of this parameter study are discussed in the following sections.

Influence of powder particle size on track formation (IN718)

To fabricate a functional thermocouple, the deposition of two dissimilar metallic tracks on the ceramic substrate is required. Therefore, pure Ni and the nickel-based alloy IN718 were investigated within this study in order to assess the influence of the powder material on track formation and substrate interaction. As first part, the deposition behaviour of IN718 was investigated. In particular, the influence of powder particle size on the thermal interaction with the ceramic substrate was analyzed.

First, IN718 tracks were deposited using the powder fraction with a particle size distribution of 20 – 63 μm. The powder mass flow rate was varied between 30 and 50 g/min, while the scan velocity ranged from 1 to 10 m/min. The laser focal position was set 1 mm above the substrate surface.

Figure 4 shows a representative metallographic cross-section of an IN718 track deposited at a scan velocity of 2 m/min and a powder mass flow rate of 50 g/min. Under these conditions, significant thermal interaction between the deposited material and the ceramic substrate was observed. The thermally sprayed YSZ layer was locally compacted, and a pronounced HAZ developed within the ceramic coating. Compared to the initial substrate condition (cf. Figure 2) partial delamination of the YSZ layer from the steel substrate occurred. In addition, vertically oriented cracks propagated through

the HAZ of the YSZ layer and terminated at the interface to the underlying thermally sprayed structure. The IN718 particles were partially molten and penetrated into the ceramic layer.

Figure 4: Metallographic cross-section of an IN718 track deposited on a thermally sprayed YSZ substrate using a powder particle size distribution of 20–63 μm.

SEM investigations further revealed that the deposited IN718 material was surrounded by a network of microcracks (cf. Figure 5). The formation of these cracks is attributed to the mismatch in thermo-mechanical properties between IN718 and YSZ, in particular differences in thermal expansion behavior, which are assumed to result in high residual stresses during cooling finally leading to shrinkage [7].

Figure 5: SEM micrograph of an IN718 track deposited on a thermally sprayed YSZ substrate, showing the metal–ceramic interface.

To better understand the thermal interaction between IN718 deposits and the ceramic substrate, as a next step a dedicated investigation was conducted to isolate the influence of powder particle size on track formation and ceramic substrate integrity. Previous work by Zhang et al. [11] demonstrated that increasing powder particle size can reduce the effective heat input into the substrate, as a larger fraction of the laser energy is consumed for particle heating and melting rather than being transferred directly to the substrate. Additionally, the temperature of the melt pool is lower due to the decreased energy powder particle volume ratio. Based on these considerations, the present study examines whether larger IN718 powder particles enable the deposition on thermally sprayed YSZ substrates with reduced thermal damage while maintaining electrical functionality.

Two IN718 powder size distributions, 20-63 μm and 60-150 μm, were investigated using identical baseline process parameters. The laser beam diameter, scan velocity, and powder mass flow rate were varied within the experimental matrix. The laser beam diameter (1.2, 1.8, and 2.8 mm), scan velocity (2-14 m/min), and the powder mass flow rate (30-60 g/min) were systematically varied.

For tracks deposited using the fine IN718 powder (20-63 μm), a HAZ within the ceramic substrate was observed under all investigated parameter combinations. Figure 6a illustrates the influence at a scan velocity of 8 m/min, a laser beam diameter of 1.8 mm and a powder mass flow rate of 40 g/min. A pronounced increase in the depth and extent of the HAZ is evident at lower scan velocities, reflecting the higher local energy input. At increased powder mass flow rates (50 g/min) and laser beam diameter of 2.8 mm and lower scan velocities (2 m/min), partial penetration of molten IN718 particles into the

porous YSZ structure is observed (Figure 6b). For scan velocities between 4 and 10 m/min at identical powder mass flow rates, the deposited tracks detached from the substrate and locally removed ceramic material. This behavior can be presumably be attributed to the degradation of the mechanical integrity of the thermally sprayed YSZ coating caused by densification and microcrack formation within the HAZ, which reduces the cohesive strength of the ceramic layer.

Figure 6 HAZ after deposition of IN718 powder with a particle size of 20 to 60 μm a) Scan velocity of 8 m/min, laser beam diameter of 1.8 mm and powder mass flow rate of 40 g/min b) Scan velocity of 2 m/min, laser beam diameter of 2.8 mm and powder mass flow rate of 50 g/min

In contrast, deposition experiments conducted with coarse IN718 powder (60-150 μm) revealed a fundamentally different interaction with the ceramic substrate. No distinct HAZ was detected in the YSZ layer for any of the investigated parameter sets. At powder mass flow rates of 50 - 60 g/min and scan velocities between 2 and 6 m/min, partial detachment of the metallic track was observed. However, this detachment occurred without measurable damage or removal of ceramic material (cf. Figure 7a). At higher scan velocities (8 – 10 m/min), powder was successfully deposited and remained locally adhered to the substrate, although the resulting tracks were discontinuous along their length (cf. Figure 7 b). These observations indicate that the increased particle size effectively reduces the thermal load imposed on the ceramic substrate, but simultaneously limits melt pool stability and continuous track formation.

Figure 7 Tracks after deposition of IN718 powder with a particle size of 60 to 150 μm a) tracks with a scan velocity of 2 – 6 m/min have detached from the substrate b) tracks with a scan velocity of 8 -10 m/min adhered to the substrate

To further improve track continuity, the influence of the distance between the substrate surface and the laser/powder focal position was examined. Previous studies by Mazzarisi et al. [12] reported an influence of this distance on the height and width of deposited tracks. While this parameter had been kept constant at 1.0 mm above the substrate in previous experiments, it was increased to modify the energy density and powder-melt pool interaction. As shown in Figure 8, increasing the focal distance to 1.4 mm resulted in flatter track geometries. Although the tracks remained discontinuous, they exhibited electrical conductivity along their entire length, suggesting that the geometric continuity is not a strict prerequisite for electrical functionality in this application. The improved electrical connectivity is attributed to the reduced track height and increased lateral material distribution, which facilitate electrical contact between adjacent deposited segments.

Overall, the results demonstrate that powder particle size is a key parameter governing the thermal interaction between IN718 deposits and ceramic substrates in DED processing. While fine powder fractions promote stable melting and track formation, they lead to excessive thermal damage of the YSZ substrate. Conversely, coarse powder fractions significantly reduce substrate heating but require careful adjustment of focal conditions and scan parameters to achieve electrically functional tracks. These findings provide an essential basis for the subsequent fabrication of Ni/IN718 thermocouples with minimized ceramic degradation.

Figure 8 IN718 with a particle size of 60 to 150 μm and a distance between substrate and laser – and powder focus point of 1.4 mm

Application of nickel tracks

Based on the observations obtained for IN718, particularly the reduced thermal impact observed for coarse powder fractions, the deposition behaviour of pure Ni was subsequently investigated using a coarse powder fraction. The pure Ni tracks were deposited using a powder particle size distribution of 60 – 150 μm . The laser power and laser beam diameter were kept constant at 800 W and 2.8 mm, respectively. Shielding and carrier gas flow rates were identical to those used for IN718 deposition (14 l/min). The powder mass flow rate was fixed at 33.33 g/min, while the scan velocity was varied between 2 and 10 m/min. This value was selected based on preliminary trials to ensure stable track formation while avoiding excessive powder accumulation on the ceramic substrate.

A representative metallographic cross-section of a Ni track deposited at a scan velocity of 6 m/min is displayed in Figure 10. In contrast to IN718 deposition, no densification or cracking of the ceramic substrate was observed. The absence of a pronounced HAZ indicates a lower thermal impact on the substrate. The Ni track exhibited continuous adhesion to the ceramic substrate. While the adhesion strength was not quantified in the present study, the observed interfacial integrity demonstrates stable bonding under the investigated conditions.

Figure 9: Metallographic cross-section of a Ni track deposited on a thermally sprayed YSZ substrate at a scan velocity of 6 m/min.

Elemental analysis by EDS was performed to examine the interface the Ni track and the ceramic substrate (Figure 11). The EDS spectra confirmed the presence of Ni within the deposited track and zirconium (Zr)-rich phases within the YSZ substrate. At the metal-ceramic interface, a minor Ni signal was detected within the ceramic, indicating limited diffusion of Ni into the substrate. However, no distinct reaction or diffusion zone was identified.

Figure 10: EDS analysis across the interface between a Ni track and the YSZ substrate.

The electrical continuity of Ni tracks adhering to the ceramic substrate was evaluated qualitatively. Electrically conductive tracks were obtained for scan velocities between 2 and 8 m/min, whereas tracks deposited at a scanning speed of 10 m/min were electrically non-conductive (cf. Figure 6). These observations indicate that, under otherwise constant processing conditions, the powder material strongly influences both the thermal interaction with the ceramic substrate and the functional integrity of the deposited tracks.

Figure 11: Ni tracks deposited on a thermally sprayed YSZ substrate at different scan velocities (2–10 m/min).

Application and testing of thermocouples

Based on the parameter studies for Ni and IN718 deposition on the thermally sprayed YSZ substrate, suitable processing conditions were identified for the fabrication of additively manufactured thermocouples using DED. The primary objective was to ensure continuous, electrically conductive tracks while minimizing thermal damage to the substrate.

Both thermocouple materials were deposited using a laser power of 800 W, a scan velocity of 8 m/min and a laser beam diameter of 2.8 mm. For both, Ni and IN718, a powder particle size distribution of

60 – 150 μm was selected. The laser and powder focal positions were set 1.0 mm above the substrate for the Ni track and 1.4 mm for the IN718 track, respectively. The powder mass flow rate was adjusted to 33.33 g/min for Ni and 60 g/min for IN718. All tracks were deposited onto the same thermally sprayed YSZ substrates used in the preceding experiments.

To fabricate the thermocouple junction, the Ni track was deposited first, followed by the IN718 track. Each track had a length of approximately 20 mm, while the track width corresponded to the laser beam diameter of 2.8 mm (cf. Figure 10). This configuration ensured a well-defined junction area and minimized the thermal load introduced during deposition of the second material.

Figure 12: Deposited Ni and IN718 tracks forming the thermocouple junction

Figure 13 shows the thermoelectric voltage as a function of temperature measured by the reference thermocouple. The conventional Type K thermoelement (orange) exhibits the expected linear relationship between temperature and the thermoelectric voltage over the investigated temperature range. In contrast, the AM Ni/IN718 thermocouple (blue) generates a consistently lower thermoelectric voltage.

Figure 13: Thermoelectric voltage as a function of temperature: printed Ni/IN718 thermocouple vs. conventional Type K reference

The observed voltage offset between the AM and the conventional thermocouple is assumed to be attributed to differences in material composition, microstructural state, and interfacial effects at the AM junction. In particular, deviations from equilibrium alloy compositions, residual stresses, and contact resistances at the junction and electrical connections are expected to influence the effective Seebeck coefficient [13]. Nevertheless, a more linear response at elevated temperatures demonstrates that the AM Ni/IN718 thermocouple provides a stable and reproducible thermoelectric signal.

Overall, these results confirm the feasibility of fabricating functional thermocouples directly on ceramic substrates using DED. Despite a systematic voltage offset relative to conventional thermocouples, the printed sensors exhibit a linear temperature response and thus represent a promising approach for localized temperature measurements on thermally loaded components without the need for mechanical machining or post-processing integration steps.

Summary and Conclusion

In the present study, the feasibility of fabricating Ni/IN718 thermocouples directly on ceramic substrates by DED was systematically investigated. The focus was placed on the transferability of process parameters, the thermal interaction at the metal–ceramic interface, and the functional performance of the additively manufactured thermocouples. Based on the experimental results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Process parameters optimized for DED of IN718 on metallic substrates are not directly transferable to metal deposition on thermally sprayed YSZ coatings. Excessive energy input leads to insufficient track formation and pronounced thermal damage of the ceramic substrate.

- Stable deposition on YSZ requires a reduced energy input. Within a narrow parameter window, continuous metallic tracks can be produced while limiting cracking, densification, and delamination of the ceramic layer.
- The powder distribution of deposited material significantly influences the thermal interaction with the substrate. IN718 with a particle distribution between 20 - 60 μm shows pronounced interaction with the YSZ coating, whereas pure Ni and IN718 with a particle distribution between 60 - 150 μm show no distinct heat affect on the ceramic material.
- Using adapted parameters, functional Ni/IN718 thermocouples were successfully fabricated by intersecting perpendicular tracks on the ceramic substrate, ensuring electrical continuity and structural integrity of the insulating layer.
- Thermoelectric testing up to 220 °C demonstrates a stable temperature response of the additively manufactured thermocouples. Although a systematic voltage offset compared to a conventional Type K thermocouple is observed, the results confirm the feasibility of the approach for localized temperature measurements after calibration.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization: Pia-Sophie Becks, Karl Michael Krämer; Methodology: Pia-Sophie Becks; Karl Michael Krämer; Formal analysis and investigation: Pia-Sophie Becks; Writing - original draft preparation: Pia-Sophie Becks; Writing - review and editing: Karl Michael Krämer, Thomas Wegener, Rüdiger Reitz, Matthias Oechsner; Funding acquisition: Matthias Oechsner; Resources: Matthias Oechsner; Supervision: Rüdiger Reitz, Matthias Oechsner

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Prof. Dr. Robert Vaßen of the Institute of Energy Materials and Devices at the Forschungszentrum Jülich providing thermally sprayed YSZ coatings and Dennis Denisov for sample preparation. Matthias Oechsner acknowledges funding by “Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft” (DFG), grant no. 523792378.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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